

1 **Discovery of E6/E7 cellular targets.**

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6 Binding and neutralization of p53 and Rb1 by E6 and E7 are the most commonly understood
7 papillomavirus oncogene functions. We performed screening for novel HPV oncogene targets in HaCaT
8 cells with stable expression of either type 16 E6 or type 16 E7 coupled with RNA-sequencing for
9 measurement of total transcription. We describe here activation of the cytokine *IL6* by HPV E6.

10 Citations

11 1. Iliopoulos, D., Hirsch, H.A. and Struhl, K., 2009. An epigenetic switch involving NF-κB, Lin28,
12 Let-7 MicroRNA, and IL6 links inflammation to cell transformation. *Cell*, 139(4), pp.693-706.

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